

A Geographical Study of Changes in Literacy in Nizamabad District of Telangana

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Abstract:

Nizamabad district is known as a backward district of Telangana state. Literacy rate in Nizamabad district is 61.25% in 2011. As per the 2001 data the same rate was 52.00%. It shows an increase of 33.02 % in the last ten years. Nizamabad mandal has the highest literacy growth rate in Nizamabad district and Gandhari mandal has the lowest literacy growth rate. According to 2001 census Gandhari mandal has the lowest literacy rate of 34.7 % in Nizamabad district while Nizamabad mandal has the highest literacy rate of 66.6 %. After studying literacy in Nizamabad district it is observed that the change witnessed between 2001 and 2011 varies from mandal to mandal between 2001 and 2011, the highest change in literacy in Gandhari mandal is 75.8 percent while the lowest change in Bhiknoor mandal is only 14.9 %. Nizamabad district's literacy has changed by 33.02 % in the last decade while Telangana state's literacy has changed by 26.60 %.

Key words: Population, literacy, Change, Development.

Introduction:

The economic development of any country depends on the literacy of that country. The economic, social and educational development of that country or district can be estimated from the level of literacy in that country or district. The countries in the world which have the highest literacy rate are known as developed countries while the countries with the lowest literacy rate are known as underdeveloped countries. Nizamabad district is known as a backward district of Telangana state. It is a district located in the north-eastern part of the state and is bordered by Telangana, The District derived its name as Nizamabad (Nizam-a-abadi) from the Nizam of Hyderabad Asaf Jahi, VI who had ruled Deccan during the 18th century A.D. Originally the District was called Indur known to have originated in the name of king Indradatta who had ruled this region during the 5th century A.D. Some of the major ancient dynasties which extended their rule to the district are Mauryas, Satavahanas, Rastrakutas, Chalukyas and Kakatiyas and in the medieval Bahamani Sultans, Qutub Shahis and Barid Shahis and in the modern period Mughals and Asaf Jahis. Nizamabad district has total 36 mandals and total population of Nizamabad district is 2551335 as per 2011 census. According to 2011 statistics, the literacy rate is 61.25 %.

Importance of Research Topic:

Education is the means of knowledge, and literacy is the means of learning. Because of this foundation of the concept tree of development. Literacy is the only highway to achieve the multifaceted goal of overall social development. Literacy rate is 100% in all the developed countries

of the world. Of course, development is seen in countries where literacy is high. That is why Indian states like Telangana, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Kerala are known as developed countries while states like Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan are known as underdeveloped. Therefore, in the present research essay, the topic of literacy in Nizamabad district has been chosen to study to review the extent of literacy in Nizamabad district.

Hypothesis:

1. Nizamabad district is educationally backward in the state of Telangana.
2. Literacy is lower in rural areas than urban areas in Nizamabad district.

Objectives:

1. To study literacy in Nizamabad district
2. To review the literacy in different mandals of the research area.
3. To study the educationally backward mandals of the study area.
4. To make a comparative study of the literacy rate of the study area and the literacy rate of Telangana state.

Data Collection and Research Methods:

Secondary sources were reviewed to study literacy in the research field. The information was collected by going directly to the District Collector's Office and District Statistical Centre of Nizamabad District. Similarly, the census of 2001 and 2011 was studied. The said research paper is based on literacy in Nizamabad district and this research paper is limited to the context of literacy and for that the period of 2001 to 2011 has been selected for this research.

$$\text{Literacy Rate} = \frac{\text{Total Literate Population}}{\text{Total Population}} \times 100$$

Study Area:

Nizamabad district is situated on the border of Karnataka and Telangana states and Telangana is on the south-west of Nizamabad district and Telangana state is on the south. Latitudinal extension of Nizamabad district is 18⁰ 05' N. to 19⁰00' and its longitudinal extension is 74⁰40' east. Longitude to 78⁰37' East. Nizamabad district is known as one of the backward districts. The total

area of Nizamabad district is 7956 sq. km. It is 2.89 % of the total area of the state. Average 900 to 1100 mm in Nizamabad district. It rained. Most of the people in Nizamabad district are engaged in agriculture business. The presented topic has been selected to study how literacy has affected economic and social development in Nizamabad district

Literacy in Nizamabad District:

Nizamabad district has total sixteen mandals out of which Nizamabad district is the most populous taluka. According to the census of 2001

and 2011 in sixteen mandals of Nizamabad district, after studying literacy, the following results have been observed.

Table 01 - Literate Population of Nizamabad District in Percentage.

Sr.no.	Mandal	2001	2011	Sr.no.	Mandal	2001	2011
01	Ranjal	46.8	59.73	19	Birkoor	42.4	52.28
02	Navipet	51.6	59.38	20	Varni	47.2	56.58
03	Nandipet	48.0	57.21	21	Dichpalle	50.3	60.29
04	Armur	58.1	67.87	22	Dharpalle	44.9	56.4
05	Balkonda	53.6	61.61	23	Sirkonda	44.0	54.27
06	Mortad	49.7	58.91	24	Machareddy	39.8	51.88
07	Kammarpalle	46.2	56.29	25	Sadasivanagar	45.4	56.3
08	Bheemgal	51.2	61.14	26	Gandhari	34.7	48.66
09	Velpur	50.4	60.93	27	Banswada	51.5	61.42
10	Jakranpalle	47.3	60.49	28	Pitlam	40.8	50.09
11	Makloor	48.0	59.31	29	Nizamsagar	43.5	50.89
12	Nizamabad	66.6	73.81	30	Yellareddy	48.8	57.1
13	Yedpalle	55.4	60.91	31	Nagareddipet	41.5	50.16

14	Bodhan	58.9	67.21	32	Lingampet	37.0	48.68
15	Kotgiri	49.5	57.1	33	Tadwai	43.1	52.58
16	Madnoor	45.0	56.85	34	Kamareddy	65.2	72.56
17	Jukkal	40.8	50.4	35	Bhiknoor	53.0	58.47
18	Bichkunda	41.5	53.36	36	Domakonda	50.9	59.74
Nizamabad District						52.00	61.25
Telangana state						60.50	67.02

Source: Nizamabad District Social and Economic Survey 2001-11

According to 2011 census in Nizamabad district Ranjal Navipet Nandipet Mortad, Kamarpalle, Makloor, Kotgiri, Madnoor, Jukkal, Bichkunda, Birkur, Varni, Dharpalle, Sirkonda, Machareddy, Sadashivnagar, Gandhari, Pitlam, NizamSagar, YellaReddy NagaReddipet, Lingampet,, Bhiknoor,

Domakoda mandals of Nizamabad district have less than 60 percent literacy rate and Armoor, Balkonda, Bhimgal, Jakranpalle, Nizamabad, Yedpalle, Bodhan, Banswada and Kamareddy mandals have more than 60 percent literacy rate.

Table 02 Change in literate population of Nizamabad district.

Sr. no.	Mandal	2001	2011	Change %	Sr.no.		2001	2011	Change %
01	Ranjal	13509	20578	52.32	19	Birkoor	17132	23236	35.62
02	Navipet	22943	29372	28.02	20	Varni	27214	36402	33.76
03	Nandipet	29393	36375	23.75	21	Dichpalle	30734	41235	34.16
04	Armoor	56963	74384	30.58	22	Dharpalle	16925	24054	42.12
05	Balkonda	35702	44764	25.38	23	Sirkonda	17480	24764	41.67
06	Mortad	24195	30043	24.17	24	Machareddy	18334	27038	47.47
07	Kammarpalle	15878	21568	35.83	25	Sadasivanaga	21269	28542	34.19
08	Bheemgal	24793	34166	37.80	26	Gandhari	14111	24808	75.8
09	Velpur	18843	23562	25.04	27	Banswada	25389	37303	46.92
10	Jakranpalle	17669	24764	40.15	28	Pitlam	14504	20764	43.16
11	Makloor	22884	30977	35.36	29	Nizamsagar	13018	16607	27.56
12	Nizamabad	213563	269126	26.01	30	Yellareddy	18728	23225	24.01
13	Yedpalle	17295	21658	25.22	31	Nagareddipet	11483	15299	33.23
14	Bodhan	66831	86176	28.94	32	Lingampet	13616	20484	50.44
15	Kotgiri	22842	28796	26.06	33	Tadwai	16595	22919	38.1
16	Madnoor	18810	29345	56.00	34	Kamareddy	59833	81890	36.86
17	Jukkal	15359	23526	53.17	35	Bhiknoor	27374	31455	14.9
18	Bichkunda	19337	29854	54.38	36	Domakonda	24220	30751	26.96
Nizamabad District							1,044,788	13,89,810	33.02
Telangana state							39,934,323	5,05,56,760	26.60

Source: Nizamabad District Social and Economic Survey 2001-11

Studying the literacy rate from 001 to 2011 shows the following results. To understand the change in literacy rate in India in detail, it is divided into three groups. In Navipet, Nandipet Balkonda, Mortad, Velpur, Nizamabad, Yedpalle, Bodhan, Kotgiri, NizamSagar, YellaReddy Birkur, Domkonda mandal of Nizamabad district, the literacy rate has changed to less than 30 percent. Armoor, Kammarpalle, Bhimgal, Jakaranpalle,

Makloor, Birkur, Varni, Dichpalle, Dharpalle, Sirkonda, MachaReddy, Sadashivanagar, Banswada and Pitalam mandals have seen a change of 30 to 50 percent literacy. Ranjal, Jukkal, Bichkunda, Madnoor Dharpalle and Lingampet mandals of Nizamabad district have seen the highest change in literacy more than 50 percent. In terms of change in literacy in Nizamabad district, Gandhri has seen the most change and Bhiknoor mandal has seen the least change.

Changes of literacy rate in Nizamabad District 2001-2011

Conclusion

A study of literacy in Nizamabad district as per the above table shows that the change in literacy in Navipet, Nandipet Balkonda, Mortad, Velpur, Nizamabad, Yedpalle, Bodhan, Kotgiri, NizamSagar, YellaReddy Birkur, Domkonda mandals is minimal. The reason for the low literacy rate in the mandal is that economic development and educational development in this mandal has not been as compared to other mandals. Ranjal, Jukkal, Bichkunda, Madnoor Dharpalle and Lingampet mandals have the highest literacy rates because of the educational and economic development in these mandals compared to other mandals. If we compare Telangana state and Nizamabad district, it is found that the increase in literacy rate of Nizamabad district is higher than that of Telangana state. Bhiknoor mandal of Nizamabad district has the lowest literacy rate of the state of Telangana, so it is necessary to pay special attention to this mandal to increase the literacy rate.

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